

ENVIRONMENT AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND GREEN TECHNOLOGIES

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SUMMARY

The article analyzes the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in environmental protection, combating climate change and its threats, as well as the development of green technologies. The possibilities of applying artificial intelligence algorithms in waste minimization, energy efficiency, smart cities and ecosystem monitoring are shown. This article also discusses the potential of artificial intelligence-based solutions to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the ethical and technological challenges they face.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, green technologies, sustainable development, environment, energy efficiency, climate change.*

INTRODUCTION

Among the rapidly developing technologies, artificial intelligence (AI) plays an important role not only in industrial and economic fields, but also in environmental protection and the development of sustainable technologies. New and smart approaches are required to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Artificial intelligence is emerging as a fast and powerful tool to meet these important needs.

Climate change, environmental pollution and the rapid depletion of our natural resources are among the most serious global problems of the 21st century. Traditional approaches to combating all these problems are no longer enough and new, more modern, smarter technological solutions are needed. Artificial intelligence (AI) is of great importance in this regard as a powerful tool for environmental protection and achieving sustainable development goals.

Artificial intelligence algorithms provide us with significant opportunities in the field of collecting, analyzing and predicting large volumes of environmental data. It is these technologies that help us to accurately monitor air and water quality, efficiently use renewable energy sources, manage virtually all types of waste, and build “Smart city” systems. At the same time, artificial intelligence applications allow for deeper and real-time monitoring of the environment.

This article explores the potential applications of artificial intelligence in the field of environment and green technologies, its contribution to sustainable development goals, and the technological and ethical issues that arise. The aim is to highlight the innovations and potential emerging at the intersection of these two important areas - technology and environmental sustainability.

2. Artificial intelligence and environmental monitoring

In modern times, environmental protection, efficient management of natural resources and combating climate change have become one of the priority issues at the global level. There is a need to apply modern technologies to effectively monitor and manage every event and change occurring in the environment. Thus, one of the most promising approaches in this field is the application of artificial intelligence technologies. AI algorithms automate the processes of collecting, analyzing and predicting environmental data, enabling more accurate and operational decision-making.

Artificial intelligence-based systems in environmental monitoring process large volumes of data from many different sources - sensors, satellite images, drone images and different weather stations - and create accurate analysis opportunities in real time. For example, we can say that processes such as air and water pollution levels, soil erosion, deforestation, greenhouse gas emissions can be monitored more accurately and continuously through artificial intelligence. All these technologies are also of great strategic importance for predicting climate change and preventing many environmental disasters.

In addition, artificial intelligence is also widely used in ecosystem protection. For example, with the help of drone images and Deep learning models, forest fires can be detected and controlled at an earlier stage. In parallel, biodiversity monitoring, tracking of rare species and behavioral (movement, growth process, etc.) analysis are also areas of application of artificial intelligence.

Artificial intelligence-based systems, through sensors and satellite imagery:

➤ Air quality analysis

Weather data management is not limited to its physical storage; this process also involves regular data updates, secure storage, and compatibility with analytical systems. In this context, database systems, visualization platforms, and API interfaces are the main technological supports. For example, real-time weather data for different regions can be obtained through open platforms such as OpenWeatherMap. The collected data is stored in SQL databases and presented to the user with tools such as Tableau and Power BI for visual analysis. At the same time, this data is included in artificial intelligence algorithms and allows for the creation of weather forecasts. Thus, the management and analysis of weather data on a scientific basis is not only a technical process, but also an important intellectual resource for effective decision-making (Rzali, 2025, p. 1)

According to the standards of the World Health Organization, the PM_{2.5} value accepted as the norm for breathing clean air in a region should be no more than 5 µg/m³. According to the 2023 report, this indicator in Azerbaijan in 2023 was 18.8, and our country ranked 52nd on the list. According to other indicators of the report, the indicators in 124 out of 134 countries and regions were above this value, which means that the population in those areas breathed completely polluted air. Among the capitals with the most polluted air, Baku ranked 45th in the world. The

places of the capitals of neighboring countries on the list are as follows: Yerevan ranked 27th, Tbilisi ranked 59th, Ankara ranked 76th, and Moscow ranked 81st.

Qonşu ölkələrin paytaxtlarının havanın çirkəlliyinə görə sırası
PM2.5 orta göstərici, 2023

Figure 1. Air pollution in the capitals of neighboring countries in 2023 (Hasanov, 2024)

➤ *Early detection of forest fires*

An uncontrolled fire that starts in a forest area is known as a forest fire, bushfire or wildfire. A significant amount of forest land is burned regularly. It becomes significantly more difficult for vegetation to grow on burned land that was once forested. This is because the ground water table decreases as the soil becomes less permeable and stops absorbing water. According to the 2008 Global Warming Report, one of the main reasons for the increase in global temperatures is the rapid spread of fires. Forest fires are often started by lightning, extremely hot and dry conditions, and careless people. One of the early detection methods is provided in this study by the use of wireless sensors (Bharadwaj, 2023, p. 1)

Figure 2. System design (Bharadwaj ,2023,p. 3)

➤ *Water resources management*

EU countries are taking measures to reduce carbon emissions under the “Green Deal,” linking water scarcity to climate change. The Azerbaijani government is also developing national strategies for more efficient management of water resources. The “Integrated Water Resources Management” program, approved in 2021, serves this purpose. New reservoirs are being built in Azerbaijan and existing ones are being modernized. This ensures more effective storage and distribution of water.

Desalination plants are planned to be built to convert Caspian Sea water into drinking water. Infrastructures for rainwater collection and use are being developed in the regions. Azerbaijan

is cooperating with neighboring countries (especially Georgia and Iran) to jointly manage border rivers and water resources. This is one of the important steps in the fight against water scarcity. These measures are important for the protection of water resources, but without international cooperation and effective policies, it will be difficult to achieve success on a global scale. To combat this problem, it is necessary to use both technological innovations and political will more. (Rafizadeh, 2024)

➤ *Forecasting soil erosion and environmental pollution*

Soil erosion is the wear and tear of the soil surface as a result of water, wind and human activities. Environmental pollution is the contamination of air, water and soil with harmful substances. These two processes are closely related to each other and are further intensified as a result of agricultural, industrial and urban development activities. Forecasting methods allow for the timely identification of these impacts and the implementation of preventive measures.

The following forecasting methods are mainly used:

1. Artificial intelligence and machine learning

- ✓ Prediction of erosion and pollution probability based on historical data
- ✓ Used in the analysis of satellite images
- ✓ Creating risk maps with GIS and AI-based models

2. Remote sensing

- ✓ Monitoring the condition of land and water resources through satellites and drones
- ✓ Preparation of NDVI and LULC maps

3. Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

- ✓ To analyze the effects of soil structure, slope, and precipitation
- ✓ Identifying the location of pollution sources

4. Physical and Empirical Models

- ✓ USLE (Universal Soil Loss Equation) – for calculating soil erosion
- ✓ SWAT (Soil and Water Assessment Tool) – modeling water and soil quality

Consequently, the application of artificial intelligence technologies in environmental monitoring is not only a scientific and technological breakthrough, but also an important tool for achieving sustainable development goals. Environmental monitoring systems equipped with such technologies can greatly benefit the establishment of a cleaner, safer and more stable environment in the future.

The connection between green technologies and artificial intelligence

Green technologies are mainly aimed at minimizing the ecological footprint (especially the carbon footprint) in energy production, transportation, and many manufacturing sectors. Artificial intelligence is applied to optimize these technologies as follows:

1. **Forecasting in solar and wind energy:** Neural networks and time series models make energy production more stable and efficient.
2. **Smart Grids:** Real-time energy demand analysis and automated distribution systems. Smart grid technology enables customers, consumers, and utilities to benefit from efficient energy management. Key features of smart grids, such as bidirectional flow, automatic recovery, energy control, and flexibility, have a significant impact on the energy sector. (**Prakash,2024, p.1**)
3. **Building energy management:** Automation of heating and lighting systems with sensor-based artificial intelligence systems (AIS).
4. ***Sustainable urban planning through artificial intelligence***

The integration of artificial intelligence and green technologies is an effective technological response to the ecological crisis. It is precisely as a result of the synthesis of these two areas that economic efficiency and social well-being increase in parallel with environmental safety. The development of smarter, cleaner and more sustainable technological solutions in the future will depend on the further deepening of this cooperation.

The smart city concept is based on ecosystems supported by SI:

- 1) Transportation optimization (*traffic flow, carbon emissions*)
- 2) Waste management (*analysis of the level of filling of garbage cans*)
- 3) Automated control systems to reduce water and energy consumption.

Discussion

Artificial intelligence, especially with its capabilities for analyzing large amounts of data and optimizing processes in real time, makes the application of green technologies more effective and targeted. For example, in the field of wind and solar energy, AI technologies make it possible to predict energy production based on weather conditions and balance energy networks. This not only prevents energy waste, but also ensures more rational use of natural resources. At the same time, in waste management, image recognition and sensor-based systems of artificial intelligence automate waste sorting, increasing the level of recycling. This creates conditions for keeping the environment clean in cities and reducing carbon emissions.

However, there are also some challenges. Large-scale implementation of AI systems requires high-quality databases, a strong computing infrastructure, and qualified human resources. In addition, questions about the ethical and transparent use of these technologies remain relevant. Open and fair approaches are needed to ensure that AI decisions are explainable and public trust is maintained.

Overall, the interaction between green technologies and artificial intelligence has great potential, both technologically and environmentally. This synergy will serve as the main basis for building smarter and more environmentally sustainable systems in the future. Research shows that developments in this area can make significant contributions not only to the environment, but also to economic efficiency and social well-being.

5. Challenges and ethical issues

The following risk factors and ethical issues should also be taken into account when applying artificial intelligence:

- Data privacy and confidentiality
- Transparency and explainability of AI decisions
- Fair and inclusive use of technologies
- The environmental impact of energy-intensive artificial intelligence models

Conclusion

As a result, the integration of green technologies with artificial intelligence plays an important role in protecting the environment and ensuring sustainable development. Artificial intelligence creates new opportunities in many areas, from energy production to intelligent waste management, by making the application of green technologies smarter, faster and more efficient. This approach not only helps to minimize environmental problems, but also helps to increase economic benefits and social well-being.

Thus, it is important to consider ethical, technical and social issues along with technological developments. In the future, the application of artificial intelligence in a more transparent, fair and public interest manner will contribute to the widespread dissemination of green technologies and the protection of ecological balance. In this regard, the connection between artificial intelligence and green technologies provides a reliable and sustainable roadmap for a green future.

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ƏTRAF MÜHİT VƏ SÜNİ İNTELLEKT: DAVAMLI İNKİŞAF VƏ YAŞIL TEKNOLOGİYALAR

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XÜLASƏ

Məqalədə süni intellektin (SI) ətraf mühitin qorunması, iqlim dəyişikliyi və səbəb olduğu təhlükələrlə mübarizə, həmçinin yaşıl texnologiyaların inkişafı sahəsində rolu təhlil olunur. Süni intellekt alqoritmlərinin tullantıların minimuma endirilməsi, enerji səmərəliliyi, smart şəhərlər və ekosistemlərin monitorinqində tətbiq olunma imkanları göstərilmişdir. Bu məqalədə həmçinin davamlı inkişaf məqsədlərinə (DİM) çatmaq üçün süni intellekt əsaslı həll yollarının potensialı və qarşıya çıxan etik və texnoloji çağırışlar müzakirə olunur.

***Açar sözlər:** süni intellekt, yaşıl texnologiyalar, davamlı inkişaf, ətraf mühit, enerji səmərəliliyi, iqlim dəyişikliyi.*

ОКРУЖАЮЩАЯ СРЕДА И ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ: УСТОЙЧИВОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ И ЗЕЛЕННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье анализируется роль искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) в охране окружающей среды, борьбе с изменением климата и связанными с ним угрозами, а также в развитии «зеленых» технологий. Показаны возможности применения алгоритмов искусственного интеллекта в минимизации отходов, энергоэффективности, «умных» городах и мониторинге экосистем. В статье также обсуждается потенциал решений на основе искусственного интеллекта для достижения Целей устойчивого развития (ЦУР) и связанные с ними этические и технологические проблемы.

***Ключевые слова:** искусственный интеллект, «зеленые» технологии, устойчивое развитие, окружающая среда, энергоэффективность, изменение климата.*